

Additional file 2. Growth curves of *E. faecium* E745 in Brain Heart Infusion (BHI) broth, heat-inactivated and native serum at 37°C. The results are the average of three independent experiments for BHI, and two independent experiments for the sera. Error bars indicate standard deviations. The arrow corresponds to the time of sampling for the RNA-seq experiments.